

Beyond Words: Emoji Patterns in Cross-Cultural Branding

Supplementary Information

Appendix-A

Table A1: Number of downloaded X messages by industry.

<i>Turkish</i>				
	Number of Messages		Messages with Emojis	
	Post	Reply	Post	Reply
Automotive	8,924	16,447	575	2,395
Financial Services and Insurance	8,210	9,328	820	897
Food Beverage	23,260	15,417	11,115	2,856
Food Service	18,027	18,424	2,780	2,307
Logistics	2,598	11,678	367	754
Personal Care	15,282	5,567	3,166	1,170
Retail	21,283	34,321	4,928	9,009
Technology	147,838	378,855	46,142	54,636
TOTAL	245,422	490,037	69,893	74,024

<i>English</i>				
	Number of Messages		Messages with Emojis	
	Post	Reply	Post	Reply
Automotive	71,046	189,724	10,751	33,974
Financial Services and Insurance	9,504	34,793	589	2,148
Food Beverage	268,053	263,449	82,322	36,074
Food Service	1,359,714	1,372,728	172,436	239,418
Logistics	60,750	193,960	5,508	17,381
Personal Care	43,206	75,307	6,541	6,810
Retail	408,465	369,228	47,363	63,390
Technology	488,136	2,892,971	193,654	386,415
TOTAL	2,708,874	5,392,160	519,164	785,610

Figure A1: Distribution of emoji frequencies
Left column: Distribution of emoji appearances. Right column: Emoji's number of appearances by their ranks.

Figure A2: Log transformed emoji frequencies ordered by log transformed ranks.
The log(frequency) to log(rank) plots do not display a straight line. Thus, we may not assume a power-like distribution along the all ranks of emojis.

Figure A3: Log transformed emoji frequencies by log transformed emoji ranks segmented into High, Moderate and Low popularity phases.

(Kejriwal et al., 2021) noted that while the log-transformed frequencies of emojis do not align in a straight line overall, segmenting the rank axis into popularity phases reveals distributions akin to power-law. Following this approach, the curve depicted in Figure A2 was divided into three distinct popularity phases (high, moderate, and low), each fitting a power-law distribution with varying parameters, as shown in Figure A3. The highest popularity phase encompasses 90% of all emoji counts in the dataset, with the moderate phase accounting for 90% of the remaining counts. To test the hypothesis that these phases conform to a discrete power-law, or Zipfian Distribution (Newman, 2005), linear regression models were applied to each phase for both languages, and R^2 values were calculated. The R^2 values, exceeding 97% as indicated in Figure A3, strongly suggest that these phases are not random but align with a Zipfian distribution, similar to word frequency distributions. The slopes correlate with the emoji popularity levels and decrease as emoji popularity decreases in both languages. For the first two segments, the minor slope differences are due to the fixed maximum x-axis values and the data size differences between the English and Turkish datasets.

Appendix-B

Comparing Diversity of Emojis Preferred across English and Turkish X Messages

Given Type Token Ratio (TTR), defined as the number of distinct words divided by the total number of word tokens in a corpus (Baayen, 2001), to measure diversity/richness of emoji preferences across English and Turkish messages:

$$TTR_i = \frac{V(C_i)}{C_i} \quad (1)$$

However, this measure is biased according to the corpus size. Larger datasets containing more textual content are more likely to produce higher TTR when compared to limited ones (Tweedie and Baayen, 1998). An approach to address this issue is applying normalization by dividing the dataset into K segments (where $K = C/N$), with each segment comprising N words (Koplenig, 2019). TTR is computed for each segment and then averaged across the segments. Given that the English dataset comprises approximately ten times more messages than the Turkish dataset, this method was adjusted to account for the difference in corpus size. Both datasets are segmented into N message chunks (where $N = 1000$), and TTR is calculated for each chunk. To ensure non-zero counts, N is chosen to be sufficiently large for the messages in chunks to contain some emojis. Ultimately, the average chunk TTR is calculated as the mean of all chunks as shown in Equation 2.

$$TTRM_i = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=0}^K \frac{V(C_k)}{C_k} \quad (2)$$

where i refers to language, $V(C_k)$ denotes the number of distinct emojis in chunk k , C_k is the total number of emojis counted in chunk k .

$TTRM_i$, ranging from 0 to 1, indicates higher values signify greater richness/diversity. To assess the significance of the difference in $TTRM_i$ between English and Turkish datasets, both a t-test and a Monte Carlo permutation test were conducted. Koplenig (2019) argues that corpora cease to be random samples when the entire known corpus of a specific context is utilized. The assumption of randomness underlying statistical tests like T-Tests is compromised when corpus data are exhaustively collected for a particular context. Consequently, traditional tests for statistical significance lose their utility, rendering generalizations about the language as a whole implausible. In this study, the objective was not to draw conclusions about emoji diversity for all English and Turkish speakers but to investigate it in branding communication. To confirm the significance of the disparity in $TTRM_i$, a modified version of Koplenig's permutation test was employed whose steps are shown in the algorithm below:

- 1: Shuffle all messages without regard to language into one dataset D
- 2: Let $f_i \leftarrow$ sampling fraction for language i
- 3: Let $s \leftarrow$ step size
- 4: Let $TTRMS_i \leftarrow$ vector of TTRM for each step s and language i
- 5: **for** $j = 1, 2, \dots, s$ **do**
- 6: Generate two random datasets: D_1 for English and D_2 Turkish proportional to f_i
- 7: Calculate $TTRM_i$ for D_i
- 8: $TTRMS_i[j] = TTRM_i$
- 9: **end for**

In the experimental setup, 150,000 random observations were sampled from the English and Turkish datasets to create dataset D . The algorithm was executed with a step size of 1000, and the selection fraction (f_i) for each iteration was set at 0.1 and 0.9, reflecting the original language distribution. The $TTRM_i$ values from 1000 iterations of this randomly generated data produced a bell-shaped distribution, enabling a comparison with the measures derived from non-random data. This method facilitated the calculation of a p-value, which represents the probability of encountering measures as extreme or more extreme than those observed in the random data. Should the p-value fall below a predetermined significance level, it could be seen as evidence refuting the null hypothesis that posits the observed differences were due to chance.

Appendix-C

The probability distribution by emotion is shown in the first two plots of Figure C1, with the last plot showing the distance between the distributions for English and Turkish messages, colored according to the sentiment of the emojis. In English, emojis were most commonly used with happy words, while in Turkish, positive emotions such as happiness and surprise were evenly distributed with negative emotions like anger, disgust, sadness, and fear. It is worth noting that even though some emojis may seem to represent a specific emotion, they are often used interchangeably with emotional words of different emotions.

Figure C1: Emotional distribution of emojis and the distance of their distributions between languages.

**top: Emotional probability distribution of emojis in Turkish, center: Emotional probability distribution of emojis in English, bottom: distance in JS divergence colored by sentiments.*

The bars in the distance plot in **Error! Reference source not found.** are colored according to the manually coded sentiment of the emojis from Novak's ranking scores (Novak *et al.*, 2015) as positive, neutral, or negative. As shown, as the distance decreases, the similarity in emotional

usage increases, and the emojis become more negative in sentiment. To understand if negative emojis are more similarly used than positive emojis in Twitter messages, we compared the mean distances by sentiment.

Appendix-D

One-variable linear regression, ANOVA, and the T-test are key statistical tools used for comparing group means and can assess differences in emoji usage between English-speaking and Turkish-speaking brands and consumers effectively. These methods are interconnected, where a T-test for two groups can be seen as equivalent to a one-variable linear regression with a binary independent variable or a one-way ANOVA with two groups. They share similar statistical calculations like effect estimation and hypothesis testing, ensuring consistent results given similar assumptions (Pituch and Stevens, 2015). A crucial assumption for these methods is the normality of the data distribution. For T-tests, the data within each group must be normally distributed to provide accurate p-values and confidence intervals (Jahan and Khan, 2012). ANOVA extends this requirement to the residuals within groups, ensuring the calculated F-statistic follows an F-distribution (Knief and Forstmeier, 2018). Similarly, in linear regression with a dummy variable, the residuals must be normally distributed to ensure precise estimation of standard errors and confidence intervals for the coefficients (Yang *et al.*, 2019). However, this assumption is violated in our dataset, where the distribution of emoji frequencies exhibits skewness and an excess of zeros.

Five regression models were developed to examine the relationship between language and emoji usage in X messages, specifically looking at the differences in mean frequencies between English and Turkish. An Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) Linear Regression model initially assessed the mean differences in emoji counts between the two languages, serving as a baseline for comparison with other models. The OLS model showed a disparity in emoji usage, quantified through parameter estimates. Subsequently, Poisson Regression (PR) was applied, suitable for count data, though it was found inadequate due to its assumption that the mean and variance of events are equal, which was not the case in the dataset. The analysis then moved to Negative Binomial (NB) regression, which accounts for overdispersion by incorporating an extra parameter, making it more accurate for this dataset where variance significantly exceeded the mean. Further, Zero Inflated Poisson (ZIP) and Zero Inflated Negative Binomial (ZINB) models were used to address zero inflation seen in the dataset. These models include a logit

model predicting the occurrence of zero emojis and a count model (either PR or NB) assessing the count of emojis when there is at least one. This dual approach allows a detailed understanding of the impact of language on the likelihood of using no emojis versus one or more.

The Stats Models library in Python was utilized to calculate the parameters of the models through Maximum Likelihood Estimation. The Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) was employed as a metric to evaluate the goodness of fit and compare the performance of the models. BIC serves as a standard measure for assessing how effectively a model aligns with a dataset, as it penalizes model complexity without being limited to a particular model type. While the actual value of BIC lacks interpretability on its own, a lower BIC value signifies a superior goodness of fit.

Table D1 shows the outputs from five models, sorted by descending BIC values. These models assess the impact of language on the mean number of emojis in an X message, dividing the data into posts and consumer replies. All models reached convergence, indicating that a maximum likelihood estimation for the parameters was successfully achieved.

The linear relationship given in Equation 1, derived from the OLS LR model (*Model-1*) involves estimates for English (base variable, intercept) and Turkish (categorical binary variable, indicating Turkish) and correlates these to the mean emoji count per message. The OLS parameters are significant for both posts and replies, indicating a significant influence of language on the emoji usage in messages. Specifically, posts in Turkish exhibit a higher emoji use than those in English by a mean difference of 0.0835, whereas replies in Turkish show a reduced emoji usage compared to English, with a mean difference of -0.0216.

Table D1: Parameter Estimates of Evaluated Models

	Posts				Replies			
	Estimate	Std. Err.	p	BIC**	Estimate	Std. Err.	p	BIC**
<i>Model-1: OLS Linear Regression</i>								
English (base)	0.2756	0.001	0.0*	6.20	0.2904	0.001	0.0*	19.0
Turkish	0.0835	0.000	0.0*		-0.0216	0.002	0.0*	
<i>Model 2: Poisson Regression (rate)</i>								
English (base)	-1.2887	0.001	0.0*	4.20	-1.2365	0.001	0.0*	9.0

Turkish	0.2648	0.004	0.0*		-0.0771	0.003	0.0*	
<i>Model 3: Zero Inflated Poisson Regression (rate, odds)</i>								
English (base, odds)	0.5977	0.002	0.0*	3.98	1.4943	0.001	0.0*	7.8
Turkish (odds)	-1.6585	0.013	0.0*		-0.1604	0.004	0.0*	
English (base, rate)	-0.2527	0.001	0.0*		0.4602	0.001	0.0*	
Turkish (rate)	-0.4740	0.004	0.0*		-0.2058	0.004	0.0*	
<i>Model 4: Negative Binomial Regression (rate, dispersion)</i>								
English (base)	-1.2887	0.001	0.0*	3.92	-1.2365	0.001	0.0*	7.18
Turkish	0.2648	0.005	0.0*		-0.0771	0.005	0.0*	
Dispersion	2.0897	0.007	0.0*		7.1159	0.013	0.0*	
<i>Model 5: Zero Inflated Negative Binomial Regression (rate, odds, dispersion)</i>								
English (base, odds)	-9.8977	2.224	0.0*	3.91	-8.0123	4.779	0.094	7.16
Turkish (odds)	-0.5118	0.014	0.0*		-1.9131	5.077	0.706	
English (base, rate)	-0.8191	0.005	0.0*		-1.2363	0.002	0.0*	
Turkish (rate)	-0.2049	0.007	0.0*		-0.0775	0.005	0.0*	
Dispersion	0.9860	0.011	0.0*		7.1146	0.018	0.0*	

* $p < 0.01$

** All BIC values are normalized by 10^6 , i.e. $4.2 * 10^6$

The analysis of emoji use per message, given its discrete count nature and deviation from normal distribution, has revealed varied outcomes across different models. The PR model (*Model 2*) marked a significant improvement over the OLS model, halving the BIC value from 19×10^6 to 9.0×10^6 , suggesting a better fit by representing the relative rate of emoji occurrences per message. The NB model (*Model 4*), while providing identical estimates to the PR model, included a dispersion parameter to handle variability, showing further improvement in BIC. Both the PR and LR models produce comparable outcomes, where brands tended to use more emojis in messages in Turkish compared to English, while Turkish consumers generally used fewer emojis.

Further analysis with ZIP (*Model 3*) and ZINB (*Model 5*) models explored the probabilities of no emojis and one or more emojis per message. The ZINB model, accommodating higher variance in counts, proved to be the most suitable, as evidenced by the lowest BIC value among the models. It showed that messages in Turkish are less likely to contain no emojis, but more likely to have fewer emojis if they contain at least one, a trend consistent across both brand and consumer communications. The ZIP model indicated a decreased likelihood of no emojis in

Turkish messages, but a lower relative rate of emojis compared to messages in English, suggesting higher emoji accumulation in English messages. The ZINB model, due to its dispersion parameter, displayed higher standard errors and broader confidence intervals, enhancing its fit to the data. Similar to the Poisson Regression model, the logit part of the ZINB model indicates that messages in Turkish are less likely to have no emojis, while the negative binomial part suggests that the probability of observing one or more emojis decreases when the message is in Turkish. However, for consumer replies, the odds parameters are not statistically significant, indicating that the observed differences in emoji usage between English and Turkish may be due to random chance.

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